

Microwave assisted facile synthesis of 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols catalyzed by stannous oxide nanoparticles

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Abstract : An efficient and facile synthesis of amidoalkyl-naphthols using stannous oxide nanoparticles as a heterogeneous catalyst under microwave irradiation in solvent-free condition is reported. This protocol is developed as a clean and safe method with short reaction time and simple work-up, utilizing a nontoxic catalyst which could be recovered and recycled.

Keywords : Amidoalkyl-naphthols, multicomponent reaction, stannous oxide nanoparticles, solvent-free, microwave.

Introduction

One-pot multi-component reactions (MCRs) by virtue of their convergence, productivity, facile execution and high yield have attracted considerable attention in recent years. MCRs involve three or more compounds reacting in a single operation without isolating the intermediates^{1,2}. One of the multi-component reactions of current interest is 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols syntheses which have potentially different biological activities³⁻⁵. The preparation of 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols can be carried out by multi-component condensation of aryl aldehydes, 2-naphthol and amide derivatives in the presence of various acid catalysts such as Ce(SO₄)₂⁶, Montmorillonite K10⁷, iodine⁸, cation-exchanged resins⁹, NaHSO₄·H₂O¹⁰, Fe(HSO₄)₃¹¹, silica supported perchloric acid^{12,13}, FeCl₃·SiO₂¹⁴ and ionic liquids¹⁵. However, some of these catalysts suffer from the drawback of green chemistry such as prolonged reaction times, low yields, toxicity and recovery and reusability of the catalyst.

Therefore, introducing clean processes and utilizing eco-friendly and green catalysts which can be simply recycled at the end of reactions, have been under permanent attention. The demand for environmentally benign procedure with heterogeneous and reusable catalysts pro-

moted us to develop a safe alternate method for the synthesis of amidoalkyl-naphthols.

Among transition-metal nanoparticles, stannous oxide nanoparticles (SnO₂ NPs) have been of considerable interest because of the role of SnO₂ NPs in making nanosensors¹⁶, electrode materials¹⁷ and as heterogeneous catalysts¹⁸. The recent literature survey reveals that SnO₂ NPs as heterogeneous catalyst has received considerable attention because it is inexpensive, nontoxic catalyst and has environmental advantages, that is, low corrosion, waste minimization, recycling of the catalyst, easy transport, and disposal of the catalyst.

In continuation of our previous studies on exploration of various methods and catalysts in organic transformations¹⁹, herein, we report a highly efficient, green and solvent-free protocol for the one-pot multi-component synthesis of 1,5-benzodiazepines using SnO₂ NPs (Scheme 1). It is noteworthy that this work has none of the above-mentioned drawbacks at all.

Experimental

All chemicals were purchased from commercial suppliers. The melting points were determined on Veego-programmable melting point apparatus (microprocessor

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols.

based) and are uncorrected. ^1H NMR spectra were obtained using Bruker AC-400 F, 400 MHz spectrometer and are reported in parts per million (ppm), downfield from tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. IR spectra were obtained with Perkin-Elmer 882 Spectrum and RXI, FT-IR model using potassium bromide pellets (in cm^{-1}). Elemental analyses for C, H and N were performed on Thermo-flash EA-1112 CHNS-O Analyzer.

General procedure for the synthesis of SnO_2 NPs :

SnO_2 NPs are prepared according to the previous literature method²⁰. The stannous hydroxyl solution was prepared by dissolving stannous(II) chloride in deionized water with a 0.1 M concentration. Then pH of the solution was maintained between 7 and 9 by adding ammonium hydroxide throughout the process. The resulting precipitate of hydrated stannic hydroxide gel was washed with deionized water more than five times till no chlorine ions were detected in the silver nitrate test. The resulting precipitate was transferred into household microwave oven with power up to 1 KW and irradiated for 15 min with 30 s intermittent time. Finally light gray coloured precipitate was filtered and dried at 120 °C by simple oven.

General procedure for the synthesis of amidoalkyl-naphthols :

A mixture of substituted aromatic aldehydes (1 mmol), 2-naphthol (1 mmol) and substituted amides (1.2 mmol) in the presence of effective amount of SnO_2 NPs (20 mol%, 0.2 mmol) were taken in 20 ml conical flask and was subjected to microwave irradiation for appropriate time in microwave oven (LG model MS1927C) at 450 W and each pulse was of 30 s with intermittent time to avoid overheating. The progress of reactions were monitored by TLC (ethyl acetate/*n*-hexane = 2 : 8). After completion, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and ethyl acetate was added. The catalyst was in-

soluble in ethyl acetate and it could therefore be separated by a simple filtration. The filtrate was collected, dried and residue was recrystallized from ethanol or subjected to column chromatography to get the pure products. All the products were identified by their ^1H NMR, IR and CHN data and compared with literature reports.

N-[(2-Hydroxynaphthalen-1-yl)-phenyl-methyl]-acetamide (Entry 1) : IR (KBr, $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 3441 (O-H, Ar, str.), 3177 (N-H 2° amide, str.), 3057 (C-H, Ar, str.), 1694 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, amide, str.), 1555–1462 (C=C, Ar, str.), 1243–1095 (C-N/C-O, str.), 770 (C-H, Ar, out-of-plane, bend), 746 (N-H, out-of-plane, bend); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 9.85 (1H, s, -CONH), 8.27 (d, *J* 12 Hz, Ar-OH), 7.97 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.69 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-H), 7.40–7.12 (9H, m, Ar-H), 2.04 (3H, s, -COCH₃); Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$: C, 78.33; H, 5.87; N, 4.81. Found : C, 77.47; H, 5.79; N, 4.76%.

N-[(4-Dimethylaminophenyl)-(2-hydroxynaphthalen-1-yl)-methyl]-acetamide (Entry 8) : IR (KBr, $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 3372 (O-H, Ar, str.), 3248 (N-H 2° amide, str.), 3084 (C-H, Ar, str.), 2924 (C-H, alkane, str.), 1652 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, amide, str.), 1581–1397 (C=C, Ar, str.), 1372–1031 (C-N/C-O, str.), 827 (CH, Ar, out-of-plane, bend), 698 (N-H, out-of-plane, bend); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 9.68 (1H, s, -CONH), 7.90 (d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-OH), 7.89–7.06 (10H, m, Ar-H), 6.73 (1H, s, -CHNH), 3.10 (6H, s, -N(CH₃)₂), 2.13 (3H, s, -COCH₃); Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 75.44; H, 6.58; N, 8.38. Found : C, 75.76; H, 6.84; N, 8.36%.

N-[(3-Nitrophenyl)-(2-hydroxynaphthalen-1-yl)-methyl]-urea (Entry 12) : IR (KBr, $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 3636 (O-H, Ar, str.), 3399–3316 (N-H 2° amide, str.), 3183–3076 (C-H, Ar, str.), 1640 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, amide, str.), 1481–1436 (C=C, Ar, str.), 1346–1068 (C-N/C-O, str.), 1528

(N-O, str.), 810 (C-H, Ar, out-of-plane, bend), 744 (N-H, out-of-plane, bend); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 8.93 (1H, s, -CONH), 8.64 (d, *J* 8 Hz, Ar-OH), 8.11–7.60 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.59–7.23 (3H, m, Ar-H), 6.88 (2H, s, -NH₂), 6.36 (1H, s, -CHNH); Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₅N₃O₄ : C, 64.09; H, 4.48; N, 12.46. Found : C, 64.16; H, 4.56; N, 12.38%.

N-[*(2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl)-(2-hydroxynaphthalen-1-yl)-methyl*]-acetamide (Entry 15) : IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 3367 (O-H, Ar, str. overlapping with N-H 2° amide, str.), 3056 (C-H, Ar, str.), 2927–2832 (CH, alkane, str.), 1640 (>C=O, amide, str.), 1595–1408 (C=C, Ar, str.), 1235–1043 (C-N/C-O, str.), 814 (C-H, Ar, out-of-plane, bend), 748 (N-H, out-of-plane, bend); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 9.68 (1H, s, -CONH), 8.45 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.88–7.04 (9H, m, Ar-H), 6.45 (1H, s, -CHNH), 3.62 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.45 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 1.87 (3H, s, -COCH₃); Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₁NO₄ : C, 71.78; H, 6.02; N, 3.99. Found : C, 71.50; H, 6.50; N, 3.90%.

Results and discussion

Initially to optimize the amount of catalyst, the reaction of 2-naphthol (1 mmol), benzaldehyde (1 mmol) and acetamide (1.2 mmol) was performed under solvent-free conditions at 480 Watt in the presence of different quantities of SnO₂ NPs. 0.2 mmol (20 mol%) of catalyst was chosen as the optimal quantity of SnO₂ NPs. The fewer amounts gave a low yield and the more amounts could not cause the obvious increase for the yield of product. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Thus, we prepared wide range of amidoalkyl-naph-

Table 1. Optimization and reusability study of stannous oxide nanoparticles^a

Entry	Amount of SnO ₂ NPs (mol%)	Time (min)/Yield ^b (%) (Microwave)
1.	5	10/68
2.	10	10/75
3.	15	10/81
4. ^c	20	10/85, 83, 82, 80
5.	25	10/84

^aReaction conditions : 2-naphthol, benzaldehyde and acetamide in the ratio (1 : 1 : 1.2 mmol); 480 Watt.

^bIsolated yields. ^cCatalyst was recycled three times.

thols under the optimized reaction conditions to investigate its scope and generality of reactions. Aromatic aldehydes bearing electron donating substituents such as 3-methoxybenzaldehyde and electron withdrawing group such as 3-nitrobenzaldehyde gave good yields. It was shown that the aromatic aldehydes with electron withdrawing groups reacted faster than the aromatic aldehydes with electron releasing group as would be expected. It was also noted that aliphatic groups reacted sluggishly and gave side products and hence desired products could not be isolated. The results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Stannous oxide nanoparticles (0.2 mmol, 20 mol%) catalyzed synthesis of 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols

Entry	R	R ₁	Product ^a	Time (min)/%yield	M.p. (°C) (Lit.)
1.	H	CH ₃	4a	10/85	242–245 (245–246) ¹⁴
2.	H	NH ₂	4b	9/86	171–172 (170–173) ^{15a}
3.	H	C ₆ H ₅	4c	10/84	234–237 (234–236) ¹¹
4.	4-Cl	NH ₂	4d	7/90	165–167 (166–168) ^{15a}
5.	4-Cl	CH ₃	4e	8/90	222–224 (223–225) ¹⁴
6.	4-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	4f	8/88	173–175 (175–177) ^{15a}
7.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	NH ₂	4g	14/82	205–207
8.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	CH ₃	4h	14/84	122–124 (123–125) ¹⁴
9.	4-CH ₃	NH ₂	4i	12/82	120–122 (118–120) ¹¹
10.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	4j	12/84	222–224 (222–223) ¹⁴
11.	4-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	4k	12/82	190–191 (190–192) ^{15b}
12.	3-NO ₂	NH ₂	4l	7/90	192–194 (194–196)
13.	3-NO ₂	CH ₃	4m	7/90	242–243 (241–242) ¹⁹
14.	3-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	4n	7/89	213–215 (214–216) ^{22b}
15.	2,5-(OCH ₃) ₂	CH ₃	4o	12/80	252–253 (251–253) ¹⁹
16.	4-Cl	CH ₃	4p	8/88	209–211

^aAll known products have been reported previously in the literature and were characterized by comparison of IR and NMR spectra with authentic samples.

Reusability of catalyst : To examine the reusability, the catalyst was recovered by filtration from the reaction mixture after dilution with ethyl acetate, washed with methanol, dried at 100 °C for 5 h and reused as such for the model reaction using SnO₂ NPs (20%) under optimized conditions (up to three cycles). It was observed that the yields of the product remained comparable in

o-QM intermediate increase the rate of 1,4-nucleophilic addition reaction because of alkene LUMO is at lower energy in the neighboring withdrawing groups than electron donating groups (EDG)²¹. Hence benzene ring with electron withdrawing groups gave better yield as compared to electron donating groups.

The XRD pattern of SnO₂ NPs is shown in Fig. 1.

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanism of action of stannous oxide nanoparticles in the synthesis of amidoalkyl naphthols.

these experiments (Table 1, entry 4) which established the recyclability and reusability of the catalyst without any significant loss of activity.

To the best of our knowledge, role of SnO₂ NPs has been proposed to activate the aldehyde by coordinating to oxygen atom which ultimately enhances the electrophilicity of the aldehyde and leads to reduction in reaction time. The condensation of 2-naphthol with the activated aldehyde give *ortho*-quinone methides (*o*-QMs) as a highly reactive and ephemeral intermediate. The same *o*-QMs, generated *in situ*, have been reacted with amide under the influence of SnO₂ NPs to form 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthol derivatives. Thus, the 2-naphthol act as Michael acceptors and araldehydes as nucleophile resulting in a Michael adduct under the influence of SnO₂ NPs. The electron withdrawing groups (EWD) substituted on benzaldehyde

Fig. 1. The XRD pattern of SnO₂ nanoparticles.

The particle size was calculated from X-ray diffraction images using Scherrer formula as follows :

$$d = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

where d is the average particle size perpendicular to the reflecting planes, K is a grain shape dependent constant (0.9), λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM), and θ is the diffraction angle. The size of SnO₂ NPs calculated using Scherrer formula varies from 14 to 60 nm. The broadening of FWHM in the XRD spectrum indicates formation of smaller particles after microwave irradiation. This is obvious as the SnO₂ NPs have been obtained by tin hydroxide NPs by dehydration.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have reported a new catalytic method for the synthesis of 1-amidoalkyl-2-naphthols derivatives by using SnO₂ NPs as an efficient, inexpensive, reusable and eco-friendly heterogeneous catalyst. The microwave solvent-free green chemistry approach offer advantages such as shorter reaction times, simple work up and excellent yield.

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